

Beauty of Magic Squares: 3240-Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 90

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The work is also available at author's site:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=17754>

Abstract

*This paper presents a systematic construction of **multiple order bordered magic squares** at orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72 and 90. for a full structural summary). Unlike classical block-wise bordered magic squares, which are built as multiples of a single block size, the structures explored here incorporate successive borders drawn from magic squares of **different orders** — specifically orders 3 through 8 — each contributing a distinct structural layer.*

*The innermost core is a magic square of order 12 formed by different-sum magic squares of order 3. Successive borders of orders 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 are then applied; **even-order borders** consist of **equal-sum**, while **odd-order borders** consist of **different-sum** magic squares. In case of order 8, first three are of equal-sums and last three are of different sums. The combinatorial multiplicity of border types at each level yields a hierarchy of distinct configurations:*

The further study of multiple order bordered magic squares of orders 108, 110, 120, 132 and 144 are given in details in the reference list.

Keywords: magic squares, bordered magic squares, pandiagonal magic squares, block-wise construction, multiple order borders, combinatorial enumeration, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

A **magic square** of order n is an arrangement of n^2 distinct integers in an $n \times n$ grid such that the sums of each row, each column, and both main diagonals are equal. This common value is called the **magic constant** (or magic sum), usually denoted S . For a magic square containing the consecutive integers $1, 2, \dots, n^2$, the magic constant is

$$S = \frac{n(n^2 + 1)}{2}. \quad (1)$$

Magic squares have fascinated mathematicians, artists, and philosophers for millennia, appearing in ancient texts. Two constructions are central to the present work.

Definition 1.1 (Bordered magic square). *A magic square is said to be **bordered** if the removal of any outermost border of cells leaves a smaller magic square. All entries are consecutive integers.*

Definition 1.2 (Block-wise bordered magic square). *A magic square is **block-wise bordered** if each border layer is not a single cell wide but is composed of smaller magic squares used as building blocks.*

During past years author [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [17, 18, 19]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [20, 21, 22, 23]. Some connection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [25, 26, 27, 28, 29]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are separated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White's web-site [3].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White's web-site [3] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [11, 12, 3].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [30].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 5 [32].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 7 [34].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 9 [36].
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 11 [38].
- **Thirteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 13 [40].
- **Fifteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 15 [42].
- **Seventeen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 17 [44].
- **Nineteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 19 [46].

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [74, 75, 76, 77, 77, 78, 79].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 4 [25, 31].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 6 [26, 33].
- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 8 [27, 35].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 10 [28, 37].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 12 [29, 39].
- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 14 [41].
- **Sixteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 16 [43].

- **Eighteen Digits:** [Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 18 \[45\]](#).
- **Twenty Digits:** [Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 20 \[47\]](#).

The advantage in working with even number multiples is that we can work with equal sums blocks of magic squares.

The aim of this work is to bring multiple order **bordered** magic squares of orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72 and 90. Let see below how it is done.

See below the details of above multiple order bordered magic square.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**

1. Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.

• **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**

1. In this case, we have considered two types of magic squares of order 4.

(a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4.

(b) The second is formed by two equal sums magic sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 resulting in a magic square of order 4. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 20

• **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

1. In this case, we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 5.

(a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5.

(b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 5, where there are two **equal sums magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner.

(c) The third is **single-layer bordered** magic square with magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 30

• **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**

1. In this case also we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 6.

(a) The first is normal magic square of order 6.

(b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 6, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

(c) The third one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 42

• **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**

1. In this case, we have considered 5 different types of magic squares of order 7.

(a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7.

(b) The second is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle and 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 .

(c) The third is a **cornered** magic square of order 7 composed of another **cornered** magic square of order 5 with magic squares of order 3 at the upper-left corner. Two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 .

(d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 with magic square of order 3 in the middle. Also there are four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 . This type of magic squares we call as **cyclic-double-layer** magic square of order 7.

(e) The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 56.

• **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 8.

(a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 formed by four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

(b) The second is a **cornered** magic square of order 8, where there is again a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal sums in each case.

(c) The third is a **double-layer bordered** magic square with **pandiagonal** with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. It has 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×8 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

(d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 with a magic square of order 4 in the middle. This magic square of order 4 is again composed two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . The magic square of order 4 also have four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×6 . Since it is formed by only **strips** of equal width, we call it a **striped** magic square of order 8.

(e) The fifth one is four equal sums magic squares of order 4, where each magic square of order 4 is formed by two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . Since it is formed by only magic rectangles of equal width it is known as **striped** magic square.

(f) The sixth one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic square of order 72.

• **6th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 9**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9.

(a) The first is composed of 9 **semi-magic** squares of order 3 resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9.

(b) The second is a cornered magic square, where magic squares of orders 7 and 5 are also **cornered** magic squares at the upper-left corner having magic square of order 3.

(c) The third is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 having **cornered** magic square of order 5 in the middle. Two **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 and two **magic rectangles** of orders 2×5 are of equal sums in each case.

(d) The forth is again a **double-layer bordered** with **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 5 at the middle. The external border is composed of 2 **magic rectangles** of order 2×9 and two **magic rectangles** of order 2×5 . Both are of equal sums in each case. In the middle there is a magic square of order 3.

- (e) The fifth is again a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 with external bordered as 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×7 . In the middle there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. This kind of magic square we call as **cyclic-type double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9
- (f) The sixth is a normal **single-layer** bordered magic square of order 9 having magic square of order 3 in the middle.

Below summarises the six construction levels.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**
 - Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.
- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**
 - In this case we have considered two different types of magic squares of order 4. Combining with magic square of order 12 we have **2-different types** of magic squares of order 20.
- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**
 - In this case, we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 5. Combining with 3 magic squares of order 20 we have **6-different types** of magic squares of order 20.
- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**
 - In this case also we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 6. Combining with 6 magic squares of order 30 we have **18-different types** of magic squares of order 42.
- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**
 - In this case, we have considered 5-different ways of magic squares of order 7. Combining with 18 magic squares of order 42 we have **90-different types** of magic squares of order 56.
- **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares. Combining with 90 magic squares of order 56 we have **540-different types** of magic squares of order 72.
- **6th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 9**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9. Combining with 540 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 540 = 3240$, i.e., **3240-different types** of magic squares of order 90.

The total count at each level equals the product of all variant counts up to that level:

$$N_{\text{ord.90}} = 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3 \times 5 \times 6 \times 6 = 3240. \tag{2}$$

More details of last border i.e., 6th border of magic squares of order 9 are given in the following section.

2 Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 90

In order to get bordered magic squares of order 90, we used following six different types of magic squares of order 9:

9x9	pan	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	9	mgc								369	
369	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369		38	43	42	50	32	27	55	15	67	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369		45	41	37	46	36	62	20	8	74	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369		40	39	44	49	33	26	56	80	2	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369		34	35	52	31	53	65	17	10	72	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369		48	47	30	29	51	23	59	14	68	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369		60	54	57	18	58	21	19	77	5	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369		22	28	25	64	24	63	61	81	1	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369		78	75	16	13	79	76	12	11	9	369
	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369		4	7	66	69	3	6	70	73	71	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369		369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

9	mgc									369	9	mgc									369		
		69	16	80	12	72	17	21	56	26	369			15	80	81	20	59	25	12	17	60	369
		13	66	2	70	10	65	61	58	24	369			67	2	1	62	23	57	70	65	22	369
		73	9	44	39	40	51	31	6	76	369			58	24	50	53	33	35	34	4	78	369
		68	14	37	41	45	53	29	79	3	369			6	76	30	40	45	38	52	54	28	369
		11	71	42	43	38	35	47	7	75	369			3	79	31	39	41	43	51	77	5	369
		78	4	33	34	50	36	52	59	23	369			72	10	46	44	37	42	36	7	75	369
		19	63	49	48	32	30	46	22	60	369			66	16	48	29	49	47	32	63	19	369
		20	62	55	25	77	8	67	1	54	369			61	18	14	13	55	71	56	73	8	369
		18	64	27	57	5	74	15	81	28	369			21	64	68	69	27	11	26	9	74	369
		369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369			369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

9	mgc									369	9	mgc									369		
		28	71	18	66	56	76	20	15	19	369			8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10	369
		54	11	64	16	26	6	62	67	63	369			1	58	54	56	21	20	18	60	81	369
		65	17	49	31	44	47	34	1	81	369			3	17	50	53	33	35	34	65	79	369
		3	79	32	40	52	36	45	61	21	369			5	19	30	40	45	38	52	63	77	369
		75	7	39	53	41	29	43	73	9	369			73	59	31	39	41	43	51	23	9	369
		60	22	37	46	30	42	50	12	70	369			71	57	46	44	37	42	36	25	11	369
		2	80	48	35	38	51	33	58	24	369			69	55	48	29	49	47	32	27	13	369
		59	55	10	74	5	4	69	68	25	369			67	22	28	26	61	62	64	24	15	369
		23	27	72	8	77	78	13	14	57	369			72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74	369
		369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369			369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

See the details:

- In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9.
 1. The first is composed of 9 **semi-magic** squares of order 3 resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9.
 2. The second is a **cornered** magic square, where magic squares of orders 7 and 5 are also **cornered** magic squares at the upper-left corner having magic square of order 3.

3. The third is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 having **cornered** magic square of order 5 in the middle. Two **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 and two **magic rectangles** of orders 2×5 are of equal sums in each case.
4. The fourth is again a **double-layer bordered** with **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 5 at the middle. The external border is composed of 2 **magic rectangles** of order 2×9 and two **magic rectangles** of order 2×5 . Both are of equal sums in each case. In the middle there is a magic square of order 3.
5. The fifth is again a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 with external bordered as 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×7 . In the middle there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. This kind of magic square we call as **cyclic-type double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9
6. The sixth is a normal **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 having magic square of order 3 in the middle.

Combining 90 magic squares of order 56 and 6 magic squares of order 8 lead us to 540 different types of magic squares of order 72. See below few examples in figures:

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Above there are only few examples, but there are 3240 magic squares of order 90 composed of magic squares orders 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9. More details are in an excel file attached with the work.

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